

Codebook

Category	Description	Example Quotes
Institutional Reputation	Statements concerning institutional reputation during the stewardship process. Examples include risks taken to get to a yes, positively viewed by news outlets, and pressure from leadership	<i>You know, the we're in the news a lot. We're a tier one research institution. We'd like it to be positive. (S5)</i>
Laws and Regulation	Statements concerning the laws, regulations, and guidance given to participants. Examples include federal laws, local state laws, and institutional policy.	<i>We are not allowed to do that, not because we know exactly what policy or regulation we will be violating...but because people fear that we might be violating some policies. (B4)</i>
Third-Party/Vendor Governance	Statements concerning the role of external vendors and contractors in data stewardship processes. Examples include vendor agreements, subcontractors, contractual obligations, and limitations on institutional oversight.	<i>there's a contractual protection, but if we don't see it holding water, it's very different than if we have seen it, you know, being held up (S5)</i>
Research Demands and Data Needs	Statements concerning researchers' objectives, expectations, and requests. Examples include changing research needs, requests for technical support, uncertainty regarding available data, and expectations for institutional assistance.	<i>So there was no clear straightforward...instruction or guidelines in terms of how to use the data (R1)</i>
Time Constraints	Statements concerning timing-related factors that influence stewardship activities. Examples include delayed engagement with data stewards, lack of awareness of available resources, rushed timelines, and additional time required to implement privacy protections.	<i>We're getting a lot of requests that are about very particular populations where we don't normally collect those students...those types of requests cost a lot of time because it's new (S13)</i>
Privacy Protection Practices	Statements concerning safeguards used to protect	<i>There's currently work being done on creating synthetic data</i>

	sensitive data. Examples include access limitations, privacy assessments, data checks, synthetic datasets, and protections based on data sensitivity and intended use.	<i>to be shared with researchers instead of actual data as a way to guarantee privacy. Which is good and bad in many ways (R3)</i>
AI in higher education	Statements concerning the use of artificial intelligence in higher education and associated privacy concerns. Examples include AI literacy, disclosure of personal information, trust in AI systems, and data governance challenges.	<i>there were cases when students interact with chat bots, they give personal information to chat bot and all that data is actually stored in a database. So there's definitely general concerns there. (B4)</i>
Stewardship Beyond Formal Responsibilities	Statements concerning data stewards performing activities beyond their formal role. Examples include researcher education, governance guidance, and regulatory interpretation.	<i>I feel like my duty is to help sort of educate people... So for me, my role is often less about saying yes or no to data access, but more about helping people ask better questions (B3)</i>
Privacy Literacy Gaps	Statements concerning limited awareness or understanding of privacy, data practices, and emerging technologies. Examples include privacy misconceptions, AI literacy gaps, and overreliance on technology.	<i>really right now the biggest threat to security and privacy is people. Yeah. And so education is key. (S10)</i>
Governance Process Maturity	Statements concerning the absence, development, or effectiveness of formal governance procedures. Examples include structured review workflows, standardized approval processes, and informal decision-making practices.	<i>When it comes to [external requests], there hasn't been much done with that right now. That's still pretty new because we're just really working to ensure that there are no legal issues (S1)</i>
Resource Constraints	Statements concerning limitations in personnel, expertise, and organizational support. Examples include shortages of experienced staff, lack of specialized expertise, and insufficient resources to support governance functions.	<i>we get more people, but then we can't meet those needs because of the resources (S11)</i>
Data Anonymization	Statements concerning the removal, transformation, or	<i>The biggest risk that...we have for on the evaluation team side</i>

	<p>protection of identifying information prior to data sharing. Examples include hashing, synthetic data, and re-identification risks.</p>	<p><i>is like leaking.. whether or not there's like an accidental phone number sent in or like a name. (R6)</i></p>
<p>Stakeholder Misalignment</p>	<p>Statements concerning differences in priorities, expectations, knowledge, and objectives between researchers. Examples include disagreements regarding appropriate data access, tensions between research utility and privacy protection, and differing interpretations of risk.</p>	<p><i>there's attempts to make the form clear to the researcher and getting the information that the team pulling the data needs. But...as you know, in research, when we design something for people, they don't always get our intentions with it and it sometimes requires several iterations (R3)</i></p>